

EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN NIGERIAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The study examined conflict management strategies and performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri, Borno State-Nigeria, and 2019-2023. The specific objectives of the study were to determine the effect of accommodating conflict management strategy, and ascertain the effect of collaborating conflict management strategy on the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested by the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 3369 non-teaching staff with a sample size of 374; this was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. The instrument of data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. Cronbach alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the questionnaire items which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data collected for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics, precisely the mean (real limits of number) and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Chi-square statistic was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that accommodating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of non-teaching staff (i.e. $c2\alpha = 812.23 > 21.03$), and also collaborating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri (i.e $c2\alpha = 712.212 > 21.03$). The study concluded that conflict management strategies positively affect the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri. It was, therefore, recommended among others that the management of the University should consider the wishes of others in conflict, smoothing over or overlooking differences to maintain harmony at the University that will enhance the performance of non-teaching staff.</p>	<p>Accommodating; Conflict; Collaborating; Performance; Management.</p>

Introduction

Organizations exist to provide goods and services that people desire. These goods and services are the products of the behaviors of workers who occupy different levels of the organizational structure. These workers also have

various backgrounds, attitudes, traits, and points of view; and these diversities have the potential to cause friction, disagreements/arguments, differences or incompatibilities, and discrepancies that if not properly managed, may lead to conflict. Conflict implies a dispute that occurs when the interests, goals, or values of different individuals or groups are incompatible with each other (Aina, Awolusi & Odulami, 2015). Thus, it involves an interactive process manifested in incompatibility, disagreement, or dissonance within or between social entities (Rahim, 2011). Conflict is, therefore, not only inevitable but omnipresent in all organizations, regardless of whether they are private or public; and when it occurs, the frustration of attaining organizational goals becomes inevitable.

Conflict in public sector organizations can manifest in the form of functional and dysfunctional conflict (Lepsinger, 2018). When functional conflict occurs within an organization, group, or team, it could enhance creativity, innovation, and team building. It could also bring about healthy and constructive criticisms, suggestions, and competitions geared towards improving one another's skills and in the long run achieve better group performance and effective organizational performance. Corroborating this assertion (Robbins, 2013) maintained that functional conflict is constructive and supportive, and can enhance organizational performance. Thus, it brings about information exchange, and honest and free expression of opinions in the organization (Rivers, 2005).

Dysfunctional conflict is destructive and tends to hinder the actualization of organizational goals. This is because, the actors in dysfunctional conflict engage in different forms of counter-productive work behavior like sabotage, and self-preservation behaviors such as withholding of information, refusing to help others, and showing a lack of interest in the shared goals (Lepsinger, 2018). It reduces employee performance, increases the chances of losing skilled personnel, leads to loss of man/machine hours and increases defective products due to a lack of employee commitment to the work (Albert, 2011). It is therefore, behoove on the management of every organization to recognize, detect, understand and handle or resolve various forms of conflict in such a way that it will promote positive organizational outcomes and minimize the chances of negative organizational effects using appropriate conflict management strategies. Conflict management strategies entail the implementation of certain strategies to reduce the bad side of conflict, and increase its positive aspects in order to increase employee performance and effectiveness in the organization (Edwin, 2013). Thus, it is concerned with the mechanisms used by organizations in resolving conflict (Adeyemi & Ademilua, 2012). Khan (2013) identified conflict management strategies namely; dominance, integrating, compromising, avoiding and obliging; while Hussein, Salem Al-Mamary and Hassan (2017) utilized five dimensions namely: avoiding, compromise, forcing, problem-solving (cooperation) and accommodating that if properly utilized will enhance the performance of the employee in any organization. Employee performance refers to the effectiveness and efficiency of an individual's work-related activities and accomplishments about their job responsibilities, goals, and standards. It is also related to activities expected of a worker and how well those activities were executed in terms of quality, quantity, and timelines (Zayum, 2018). The indices of employee performance in an organization may include, the quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence at work, and cooperativeness with others. Miner (1988) cited in (Achmad Faisal *et al.*, 2017) opined that employee performance can be measured; Firstly, the quality of work by looking at the error rate, the extent of damage and the accuracy of work; Secondly, the quantity, the numbers of jobs generated; Thirdly, the use of time in the work indicated by absenteeism, tardiness, effective work time/working hours lost; Fourthly, cooperation with others in the works.

The University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID) was established in 1975 and saddled with the mandate of teaching and research in the field of Basic Arts and Sciences, aims at excellence in Agriculture, Pastoralism, Engineering,

Human and Veterinary Medicine, and Information Technology as well as in Arid Zone, Trans-Saharan and Inter-African Peace and Strategic Studies. The University has the following colleges/faculties namely: College of Medicine, Faculty of Agriculture, Arts, Environmental Sciences, Allied health sciences, Basic medical sciences, Dentistry, Education, Engineering, Law, Management sciences, Sciences, Pharmacy, Social sciences, and Veterinary medicine. The University also aims to promote the development of Private and Public morality, discipline, accountability and probity, and also international cooperation through participation, research and dissemination of information. Just like any public sector institution in the country, the University of Maiduguri is a meeting place for various individuals with different backgrounds, traits, attitudes, and perspectives; the association/socialization of the workers cannot be conflict-free in the said institution. The study is motivated by the researcher's constant worries over the incessant conflict being experienced in the University between the University management and the non-teaching staff union. There seem to be no appropriate strategies for resolving them and the attendant consequences these have on workers' morale will eventually reflect on employee performance in terms of the quality of work produced, the quantity of work produced, and the timeliness of work produced to the public. However, the extent to which conflict management strategies affected the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria, 2019-2023, is therefore, the focus of the study.

Statement of Problem

Public sector organizations in Nigeria, in recent times, have witnessed a plethora of trade disputes rather than peaceful industrial relations between employers and employees. The pattern of industrial relations has been conflictual with disruptive consequences and significant work-hour losses due to work stoppages. In the literature, on labor unrest, the causes of industrial conflict in public sector organizations revolve around the recalcitrant attitude of the management towards workers, poor policy choices, and failure of the government to respond to and respect existing agreements already signed with labor unions (Oghenekaro, 2013). This action leaves the employees with low morale, a decrease in service delivery, the quantity of work produced, quality of work produced; an increase in absenteeism, defective products due to lowered commitment to work, and health issues due to stress and depression (Nwadike, 2019).

Conflict management strategies are necessary to maintain sanity and cooperation in public sector organizations that will enhance effective organizational performance to the public. When public sector organizations are not able to manage conflict effectively and adopt appropriate strategies, it may affect employee performance in terms of the length of service, quality, and quantity of work produced by the organization to the public. To achieve effective employee performance in public sector organizations, the management of public organizations needs to know the underlying causes of conflict. If the causes of organizational conflict are known, a conflict chart that directs management processes can be easily developed. This can enable the organizations' management to adopt appropriate strategies towards managing such conflict for effective performance to the public.

However, observations have shown that the management of the University of Maiduguri has evolved several conflict management strategies such as accommodating and collaborating over the years to handle or resolve various forms of conflict in such a way that it will minimize the chances of negative organizational effects and promote positive organizational outcomes that will ensure effective employee performance in terms of the quality of work produced, the quantity of work produced and the lengthen of service delivery to the public. Yet, there appears to be low employee turnover, low morale, reduced productivity, reduction in quality and quantity of work produced, passive/aggressive behavior, and general distrust among the workers. What then are the causes of these

negative organizational behaviors' which appear to be undermining the conflict management strategies adopted by the management of the University of Maiduguri? Against this backdrop, the study examines the effect of conflict management strategies on the performance of non-teaching staff with specific reference to the University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the effect of conflict management strategies on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. determine the effect of accommodating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri; and
- ii. Ascertain the effect of collaborating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested by the study:

- i. Accommodating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.
- ii. Collaborating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 3369 employees which comprised 1435 senior and 1934 junior Non-teaching Staff of the University of Maiduguri. The sample size for the study was 374; this was determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers from the literature reviewed. The responses to each item in the questionnaire were based on a 4-point scale of very high extent, high extent, low extent and very low extent with a corresponding nominal value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the internal consistency of the questionnaire items which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81 indicating that, the instrument is highly consistent and hence reliable for the study. A total of 374 copies of the questionnaire were administered by the researchers and only 350 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved from the respondents and used for the data analyses. Data collected for the study were analyzed using a descriptive statistic of the mean (real limits of numbers) and standard deviation, while the Chisquare statistic was used to test the stated hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

In answering the research questions, the real limits of numbers were used for decision-making as follows; 3.50 - 4.00 = very high extent; 2.50 – 3.49 = high extent; 1.50 – 2.49 = low extent; 1.00 – 1.49 = very low extent.

The decision rule for rejection of the stated hypotheses was based on the Chi-square calculated value ($c2\alpha$) and the critical value. A hypothesis of no significant effect was rejected for any cluster of items whose $c2\alpha$ was less than the critical value at 0.05 and with the specified degree of freedom while it was not rejected for any cluster of items whose $c2\alpha$ was greater than the critical value at 0.05 and with the specified degree of freedom.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for the study comprised two variables-independent variables and a dependent variable. The independent variables were accommodating and collaborating conflict management strategies while the dependent variable was performance.

Conflict

The term conflict has acquired a variety of definitions over the years, but most researchers agreed that it is best defined as an interactive process manifested in incompatibility, disagreement or dissonance within or between social entities. Robbins (2013) viewed conflict as a process that begins when one party perceives that another party has negatively affected or is about to negatively affect something that the first party cares about. Conflict refers to some form of friction, disagreement, or discord arising within a group when the beliefs or actions of one or more members of the group are either resisted by or unacceptable to one or more members of another group (Dontigney, 2013). Therefore, conflict can be viewed as an interactive state in which the behaviors or goals of one actor are to some degree incompatible with the behaviors or goals of some other actor or actors in an organization. Consequently, every organization should as a matter of urgency, devise strategies for managing conflict, seeing that they are unavoidable in any human organization and can hinder or promote effective organizational performance.

Conflict Management Strategies

Since conflict is part and parcel of human life and is inevitable in work organizations, there is a need for management strategies that would curtail the negative effect and increase the positive effect. Conflict management strategies are the measures, approaches or methods that organizations use to manage conflict to enhance organizational performance. They are also considered mechanisms used by organizations in resolving conflict (Adeyemi & Ademilua, 2012). Rahim (2002) opined that conflict management strategies are concerned with the adoption of effective approaches to undermine the dysfunctional implications of conflict while enhancing its functional aspect to improve the learning and effectiveness of the organization. Khan (2013) identified conflict management strategies as; dominance, integrating, compromising, collaborating, avoiding and obliging; while Hussein, Salem Al-Mamary and Hassan (2017) utilized five dimensions namely: avoiding, compromising, forcing, problem-solving (cooperation) and accommodating. Therefore, the study, adopted two dimensions of conflict management strategies (i.e. collaborating) from the work of (Khan, 2013) and (accommodating) from the work of Hussein, Salem Al-Mamary and Hassan (2017) as variables of the study.

Accommodating Strategy

This strategy of conflict management entails giving the opposing side what it wants to resolve conflict in good harmony (Dontigney, 2013). It also involves minimizing or suppressing real or perceived differences while focusing on the other's views of the situation (McNamara, 2013). According to Schermerhorn (2000) cited in Momanyi and Juma (2016), an organization that uses using accommodating conflict management strategy tends to be cooperative but assertive. They agree to the wishes of others, smoothing over or overlooking differences to maintain harmony within an organization. It results in a lose-win solution and a good relationship between parties in conflict is created. According to Hellrigel and Slocum (1996) cited in Momanyi and Juma (2016), this relationship is created when people appeal for cooperation and try to reduce tension and stress by offering reassurance and support for the other person's views. Kraybill (2005) refers to accommodating strategy as a harmonizing conflict response. The harmonizing strategy has a low focus on the agenda and a high focus on the relationship. It is a strategy of conflict management in which one party gives in to the wishes or demands of another in conflict (Riaz, 2010).

This conflict management strategy aims to yield, and often to maintain the relationship or status quo between themselves and the other party (Rahim, 2011). This strategy of conflict management is considered to be empathydriven because of its non-assertive nature. It is sometimes referred to as the smoothing strategy (Hussein,

Salem AlMamary & Hassan, 2017). Therefore, the accommodating strategy seeks to provide a solution to conflict situations by neglecting one's demand or interest just to satisfy the demand of the other party.

Collaborating Strategy

Collaborating strategy is a method of conflict management in which a person tries to work together with the other person (Crystal, 2007). Kofman (2015) refers to it as constructive collaboration. He asserts that this approach reveals people's preferences and constraints, and engages everyone in constructing solutions that go beyond the original alternatives. It maximizes efficiency through cooperation. Constructive collaboration allows people to express and understand each other's needs and create new solutions. It addresses the task through consensual decision-making, the relationships through mutual respect, and each individual's self-worth through the consideration of his needs and values. It involves finding a solution to the conflicting situation that satisfies both parties (Thomas & Kilmann, 1974). The collaborating strategy also refers to assertiveness and cooperativeness as it allows both party's goals to be completely achieved by putting the concerns of both parties into consideration (Oluwakemi, 2016). Mughal and Khan (2013) opine that collaborating strategy enables people to take time to listen to others to find the best solution to handle the conflict. It is aimed at satisfying the needs of the parties concerned especially when the members have mutually significant goals (John-Eke & Akintokunbo, 2020). Collaborating strategy is applicable when both parties desire to solve the problem and are willing to work together toward a mutually acceptable solution.

Employee performance

Employee performance could simply be understood as the related activities expected of a worker and how well those activities were executed in terms of quality, quantity, and timelines (Zayum, 2018). The indices of employee performance in an organization may include, the quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence at work, and cooperativeness with others.

Bond and Fox (2007) also highlight the indices of employee performance in an organization as follows: the quantity of work, timeliness of work, quality of work i.e the quality of work produced in terms of standards, use of resources/efficiency, self-reliance, productive work habits, alignment and compliance with organizational objectives. Afshan *et al.*, (2012) define employee performance as the achievement of specific tasks measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. It also refers to how a member of staff performs their duties, complete required tasks, and behave in the workplace, as measured by the quality, quantity, and efficiency of work (Upadhaya *et al.*, 2014).

Miner (1988) cited in (Achmad Faisal *et al.*, 2017) states that employee performance can be measured; Firstly, the quality of work by looking at the error rate, the extent of damage and the accuracy of work; Secondly, the quantity, the numbers of jobs generated; Thirdly, the use of time in the work indicated by absenteeism, tardiness, effective work time/working hours lost; Fourthly, cooperation with others in the works.

Therefore, employee performance can be defined as how an employee fulfils their job duties and executes their required tasks in terms of effectiveness, quality, quantity, timeliness, and efficiency of output per the responsibilities given to him/her.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Cooperative and Competitive Theory developed by Deutsch (1949) as its theoretical base. The theory posits that achieving effective employee performance in an organization through conflict management strategies is determined by the principles of cooperative and competitive. A cooperative principle aligns with the process of interest-based or integrative bargaining, mutual benefit, interdependence, collaboration, trust, open and

honest communication, equal status and influence, and sharing common goals and values, which leads parties to seek win-win solutions. Thus, it involves helpful, supportive, and integrative actions that in turn help the team succeed at its task and strengthen relationships among employees. Whereas, the competitive principle aligns with the process of distributive bargaining, individual benefit, independence, competition, distrust, limited communication, unequal status, and conflict of goals and values, which results in win-lose outcomes. It also implies an opposition in the goals of the interdependent parties such that the probability of goal attainment for one decrease as the probability for the other increases.

The theory equates a constructive process of conflict resolution with an effective cooperative problem-solving process in which the conflict is a mutual problem to be resolved cooperatively. It also equates a destructive process of conflict resolution with a competitive process in which the conflicting parties are involved in a competition or struggle to determine who wins and who loses; often, the outcome of the struggle is a loss for both parties (Johnson & Johnson, 1989). Thus, cooperative induces and is induced by perceived similarity in beliefs and attitudes, readiness to be helpful, openness in communication, trusting and friendly attitudes, sensitivity to common interests and deemphasis of opposed interests, orientation toward enhancing mutual power rather than power differences, and so on. Similarly, competition induces and is induced by the use of tactics of coercion, threat, or deception; attempts to enhance the power differences between oneself and the other; poor communication; minimization of the awareness of similarities in values and increased sensitivity to opposed interests; suspicious and hostile attitudes; the importance, rigidity, and size of issues in conflict; and so on.

In applying this theory, the management of the University of Maiduguri should focus more on the cooperative principle rather than the competitive principle to ensure effective employee performance at the University.

Result and Discussion

The data obtained during the field survey from the Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri were presented and analyzed in this part of the paper using a descriptive statistic of the mean (real limits of numbers) and standard deviation.

Table 1: Returned and not-returned questionnaire

Respondents	Number Distributed	Number Returned	Number Not Returned	% of Total Returned	% of Total Not Returned
Senior Staff	159	152	7	40.64	1.87
Junior Staff	215	198	17	52.94	4.55
Total	374	350	24	93.58	6.42

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Table 1 above shows that out of the 374 copies of the questionnaire administered by the researchers, 350 (93.58%) valid questionnaires were retrieved, while 24 (6.42) questionnaires were not returned. Based on that, 350 copies of the questionnaire were used for the data analysis.

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Effect of Accommodating Conflict Management Strategy on the Performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

S/N	Statements	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
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1.	The University satisfy the expectations of the employee in handling conflict that enhances their performance	350	1.00	4.00	3.42	.534	High extent
2.	Accommodating employee's views in resolving conflict amicably motivates employees to put on their best for maximum performance	350	2.00	4.00	3.79	.553	Very high extent
3.	The University always go along with the suggestions of employees in solving conflicts that will affect their performance positively	350	1.00	4.00	3.83	.572	Very high extent
4.	Management of the University seeks consent and approval and is eager to help and support in resolving conflict	350	1.00	4.00	3.61	.551	Very high extent
5.	The management of the University sacrifices self-interests to satisfy the needs of employees for maximum outputs	350	2.00	4.00	3.68	.569	Very high extent

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Data presented in Table 2 revealed that all 5 items had their mean values ranging from 3.42 to 3.83 which were real limits of 3.50 to 4.00. This shows that the accommodating conflict management strategy affects the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri to a very high extent. The table further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from .54 to .56, indicating that the respondents were not too far from the mean and the opinion of one another in their responses on the extent to which accommodating conflict management strategy affects the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Effect of Collaborating Conflict Management

Strategy on the Performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

S/N	Statements	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
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6.	Management of the University embracing dialogue in managing conflict results in positive conflict outcomes that affect employee performance positively	350	1.00	4.00	3.50	.549	Very high extent
7.	The University management joins the ideas of conflicting parties to achieve the best solution in resolving conflict that will bring best in employees	350	1.00	4.00	3.58	.553	Very high extent
8.	Collaboration helps in the achievement of mutual outcomes in	350	1.00	4.00	3.56	.550	Very high extent
	conflict given its focus on building relations and integrating solutions						
9.	It improves the quality of decisionmaking under stress and reduces the amount of re-work required affecting employee performance positively	350	1.00	4.00	3.61	.561	Very high extent
10.	The University management collaborates with employees in resolving conflict for maximum performance	350	2.00	4.00	3.76	.563	Very high extent

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Data presented in Table 3 revealed that all 5 items had their mean values ranging from 3.50 to 3.76 which were real limits of 3.50 to 4.00. This shows that collaborating conflict management strategy affects the performance of Nonteaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri to a very high extent. The table further showed that the standard deviation of the items ranged from .54 to 56, indicating that the respondents were not too far from the mean and the opinion of one another in their responses on the extent to which collaborating conflict management strategy affects the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Test of Hypotheses

In testing the stated hypotheses of the study, the Chi-square statistic was used at a 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis one

Accommodating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

To test hypothesis 1 above, the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of accommodating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri were analyzed using the Chi-square statistic with the aid of Micro-Soft Excel and presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test on the Effect of Accommodating Conflict Management Strategy on Performance of Nonteaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

	Df	c2	c2 α	Sig.	Alpha Level	Remark
Pearson Chi-square	12	21.03	812.231	.000	.05	S, R
Number of Valid Cases		350				

Df = degree of freedom, c2 = critical value, c2 α = chi-square calculated, Sig. = P-value; P < .05, S= Significant, R= rejected.

Table 4 shows a Chi-square calculated value of 812.23 which is greater than the critical value of 21.03 at a .05 level of significance and with 12 degrees of freedom (i.e. c2 α = 812.23 > 21.03). This indicates that accommodating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri during the period under review. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that accommodating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri, was rejected.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of Responses of Senior and Junior Staff on the Effect of Accommodating Conflict Management Strategy on Performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t-cal	Sig.	Remarks
Senior Staff	152	3.5232	.37053	.04951	12	.044	.868	NS, NR
Junior Staff	198	3.7715	.66798	.04687				

N= Number of respondents, Std = Standard deviation, df = degree of freedom, t-cal = t-calculated, Sig. = P-value; P > 0.05, NS = Not significant, NR = Not rejected.

Table 5 above shows a p-value of .868 which is greater than the alpha value of .05. This indicates that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings of responses of senior and junior staff on the effect of accommodating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Hypothesis two

Collaborating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

To test hypothesis 2 above, the mean ratings of respondents on the effect of collaborating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri were analyzed using the Chi-square statistic with the aid of Micro-Soft Excel and presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Chi-Square Test on the Effect of Collaborating Conflict Management Strategy on Performance of Nonteaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

	Df	c2	c2 α	Sig.	Alpha Level	Remark
Pearson Chi-square	12	21.03	712.212	.000	.05	S, R
Number of Valid Cases		350				

Df = degree of freedom, c2 = critical value, c2 α = chi-square calculated, Sig. = P-value; P < .05, S= Significant, R= rejected.

Table 6 shows a Chi-square calculated value of 712.212 which is greater than the critical value of 21.03 at a .05 level of significance and with 12 degrees of freedom (i.e. c2 α = 712.212 > 21.03). This indicates that the collaborating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri during the period under review. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that collaborating conflict management strategy has no significant effect on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri was rejected.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of Responses of Senior Staff and Junior Staff on the Effect of Collaborating Conflict Management Strategy on the Performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri

Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Mean Error	Df	t-cal	Sig.	Remarks
Senior Staff	152	3.6371	.35136	.04695	12	.192	.737	NS, NR
Junior Staff	198	3.6490	.41757	.03174				

N= Number of respondents, Std = Standard deviation, df = degree of freedom, t-cal = t-calculated, Sig. = P-value; P > 0.05, NS = Not significant, NR = Not rejected.

Table 7 above shows a p-value of .737 which is greater than the alpha value of .05. This indicates that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings of responses of senior and junior staff on the effect of collaborating conflict management strategy on the performance of Non-teaching Staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Discussion of Findings

The study examined conflict management strategies and performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri, Borno State, 2019-2023, and statistically analyzed the views of 350 employees of the institution. The results of the study in Table 2 showed that accommodating conflict management strategy affects the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri to a very high extent with all 5 items having their mean values ranging from 3.42 to 3.83. The findings from research question 1 in Table 2 were further supported by findings from hypothesis 1 in Table 4 which revealed that accommodating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri (i.e. c2 α =

812.23 > 21.03). The findings of the study were also supported by the t-test in Table 5 which revealed that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings of responses of senior staff and junior staff on the effect of accommodating conflict management strategy on performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri.

The findings from research question 2 in Table 3 revealed that 5 variables of collaborating conflict management strategy affect the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri to a very high extent with all 5 items having their mean values ranging from 3.50 to 3.76. The findings from research question 2 in Table 3 were further supported by findings from hypothesis 2 in Table 6 which revealed that collaborating conflict management strategy has a positive significant effect on the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri (i.e. $c2\alpha = 712.212 > 21.03$). The findings of the study were also supported by the t-test in Table 7 which revealed that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings of responses of senior staff and junior staff on the effect of collaborating conflict management strategy on performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri.

Conclusion and Recommendations

An organization is established to achieve certain defined objectives or goals. Thus, the success or otherwise of an organization in achieving its desired objectives or goals to an extent is usually determined by the effectiveness of the organization in adopting an appropriate conflict management strategy that will enhance its performance. Conflict management forms an integral part of any organization that wants to succeed because if not well taken care of, the organization may be heading towards doom in terms of performance. From the findings of the study, it therefore concludes that the variables of conflict management strategies such as (accommodating and collaborating) have a positive significant effect on the performance of non-teaching staff at the University of Maiduguri.

The study, therefore, recommended that management of the University of Maiduguri should consider the wishes of others in conflict, smoothing over or overlooking differences to maintain harmony at the University that will enhance the performance of non-teaching staff. The management of the Institution should adopt an inclusive and collaborative conflict management strategy to guarantee the effective performance of non-teaching staff at the University.

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